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The Impact of Built Environment on Human Behaviors

Amira Mersal Mahmoud¹¹Higher Institute of Engineering and Technology, King Mariout

Abstract

This study discusses the relationship between the physical environment and the behavior of its inhabitants in traditional cities (The Old City of al-Quds). It analyses the effects of a particular physical environment on the different aspects of the lives of its people as well as their interactive influence and changes of the features of the environment within which they are living. The built environment should adapt to their different needs in this rapidly changing era of technological revolution in order to understand how does that old urban fabric, which was originally formed as a reflection and translation to a past culture, emphasize the importance of utilizing the knowledge of human behavior while designing built environments. It also discusses the role of architects in the psychological space design and formation of appropriate and inappropriate behavioral patterns.

This study mainly aims to shed light on housing in the Old City of al-Quds in particular, a city that has witnessed continuous decline in its standards and requirements of living in terms of the functional, social, educational psychological and health aspects of the population in order to examine the relationship between the population and the physical environment. This is done by analyzing the specific architectural style of the housing environment with its particular formation, elements, and characteristics, and their influence on the people's traditions, values, social relations. The study concludes that the existing situation of the residential environment in the old city has lost much of its cultural values that forms the link between the cultural and social identity of the inhabitants and the architectural style of the physical fabric of housing. It also shows that the reality of its existing situation has a negative impact on residents' characteristics and on their different life issues. While sometimes keeping part of the original features, the study recommends that upgrading housing use within the old city in Al-Quds, is one of the most important factors not only to save the old city, but also to revive the cultural values associated with our cultural heritage and national identity. This could be achieved by applying various programs among people to support them, promote their living conditions, raise awareness, and strengthen their national affiliation. This will also lead to reversing the decline in historic monuments that are closely linked not only to the peoples' own civilization, but also to their historic rights in this land.

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Keywords

human behavioral; environmental psychology

1. Introduction

Because the needs of humans are vast and ever changing, it is vital that designers be informed about the relationship of the people with their built environment (Lang, 1987). The understanding of this mutual relationship between

people and their surroundings is the major concern of behavioral sciences (Dent, 1998). Human behaviors, attitudes and values become significant in order to create enabling environments for the diverse needs of people in the contemporary society (Dent, 1998; Churchman, 2002). In this respect, the main aim of this paper is to emphasize the importance of utilizing the knowledge of human behavior while designing built environments and to approach this issue from the perspective of an interdisciplinary discourse: environmental psychology.

Nowadays, it is quite a necessity to use the behavioral sciences and environmental psychology findings in the field of architecture. Theoretical knowledge in the field of architecture has always been in need of some frameworks in order to facilitate theory development, criteria preparation and review of architectural products and process. Behavioral science is one of the disciplines that can provide the framework and theoretical background for architecture.

Generally, using behavioral sciences in the process of architectural design increases the quality of the final product. The interaction between the physical environment and health has been of interest to epidemiologists. However, until recently, psychologists have tended to define the role of the environment in the determination of behavior and the psychological and physiological effects of these concepts on the behavior of an individual (Tala, 2008). Naturally, knowledge and understanding of these concepts will be of vital importance to the environmental designers.

2. Environmental Psychology

Environmental psychology is the study of the relationships between behaviors and experiences of a person and his/her built environment. Looking at the historical background “the topic under that label includes perception n theory, cognition, social and anthropological psychology, the study of social relationships and the study of culture” (Lang, 1987). Therefore, the next parts of this paper expand the issue of environment-behavior relationship by analyzing the factors changing this framework, like the globalization process.

An important aspect concerning the definitions of environmental psychology is made by emphasizing the reciprocal action between an individual and his/her surrounding . In his book, *Environmental psychology: principles and practice*, Gifford defines environmental psychology as “the study of transactions between individuals and their physical settings” (Gifford, 2002). While inquiring about the definitions of the field of environmental psychology, it is important to highlight that environmental psychology is included within the person-environment theory and goes under the topic of behavioral sciences (Land, 1987; Gifford, 2002; Bonnes & Secchiaroli, 1995).

One of the definitions of environmental psychology is assessing the built space i.e. whether or not the space satisfies the designer’s goals. In environmental psychology the human reaction to the environment is studied (Bonnes & Secchiaroli, 1995). Environmental Psychology helps the architect to design a built environment that caters to the needs of the people. During the 1950’s, 60’s and 70’s, architects considered the needs of the people (Jahanian & Motalebi, 2013).

All the aforementioned definitions of environmental psychology highlight the significance of understanding this reciprocal relationship and of using this knowledge in order to be able to mitigate a variety of problems (Dent, 1998; Gifford, 2002). Within the framework, it is also important to describe this mutual relationship in more detail and expand the meaning of place attachment and sense of place. Thus, the study brings clarity to the issue of how people perceive, feel, sense and interact with their surrounding environments.

3. Human Perception of the Urban Environment

The interaction of individuals with the spatial environment depends on the extent of the individual’s perception of the vacuum and the way he or she absorbs the environment around him or her. The individual perceives the environment around him or her through the following levels (Ittelson, Proshansky, Rivlin & Winkel, 1974):

- The geographical environment: The global content of the general perception of the individual and the interactive environment of individuals

- The interactive environment: It is a component of the parts that collide with the human in his or her dealings, and the parts of perception is the environment known to man
- The aware environment: which depends on current indicators and past experiences
- Behavioral environment: represents the part closest to the individual, which is part of the perceptible environment of the individual and determines his or her behavior towards the environment.

We conclude from this that dealing with the environment does not only include the effect of the environment on man, but also includes the reflection of man's behavior on the environment around him or her, i.e., the effect of reciprocity. The environment affecting human beings must include several variables taken into account such as culture, social status, ethnic groups, family relations and lifestyle. These factors represent the environment around man (fig 1) and this environment consists of all human and material elements, social and cultural structures, and psychological influences that surround the elements of the environment in the vacuum of the individual (Sharif, 1992).

Figure 1. The relationship between mental and behavioral activities and their impact on understanding and dealing with the environment

4. The Relationship Between Human Behavior and the Environment

In this context, knowing and understanding of every day lives plays an important role while designing the physical environments. Gifford (2002) explained this importance with the keywords of perception and cognition. Environmental perception is related to the reinterpretation of the gathered data by users in the way that they store, transform, organize, forget, and recall knowledge (Gifford, 2002). The individual concerns about the built environments, which Gifford called environmental attitude, also became significant in terms of environmental psychology.

Understanding the concepts of preference, cognition and place attachment are important factors changing the framework of environmental psychology as well as of architecture and planning while designing built environments and relating everyday environment to the human behaviors. It should also be noted that besides preference, cognition and place attachment, there is also impact of information and communication technology (ICT) on human behaviors and their relationship to their everyday life because "ICT is transforming all aspects

of society"] (Selwyn, 2004). By referring to the term ICT and its relationship to our surrounding environment, it is possible to state that the physical environment is changing more rapidly and using and distribution of all technologically based products and environments can affect all of the human behaviors and attitudes (Fozard, Rietsema, Bouma & Graafmans, 2000).

The control of space can be achieved through habitual occupation, some form of defense, personalization and mere marking. Psychological well-being, feelings of security and safety act on people's attitudes and the indicators of environmental psychology depend on the user's perception of space as territory (Newman, 1972; Grifford, 1997). In countries with high urban crime rates, the feelings of security are often expressed through territoriality attitudes. The control of space is considered vital for physical safety and prevention of crime. Fences, walls, and security bars are all signs of defense attitudes.

With regards to human behaviors, individuals can be forced to show certain behavior but surely such ways for making behavioral changes will not be useful. Instead, they will result in mental reactions such as separation from the environment or external reactions such as changes in the environment. This is due to the fact that individuals always try to use their own methods until they are justified not to and if they are forced to do an action, they will become aggressive (Selwyn, 2004).

“The behavioral sciences can help us to understand the present and what the trends in society are, they can help us to predict the outcomes of our design proposals for the future better than we do now” (Lang, 1987). With the help of the study of environmental psychology, it is possible to reduce the uncertainty of architects, interior designers and urban planners while making decisions on users’ needs during the design process. Moreover, it is also possible to improve their designs by taking account the environmental research results and incorporating the findings to the design proposals. Finally, “useful information must be located, and it must be translated from the terminology of human sciences to the language of design” (Motalebi, 2003; Deasy, 1974).

Personal space, as defined in environmental psychology, is the distance and orientation component of interpersonal relations. Cultural differences exist. Also when physical settings are less spacious, interpersonal distances increase. Crowding, therefore, affects this concept.

If individuals lose their perception of the environment and the criterion for judging it, architecture will not have any achievements. The reason is that architecture is a direct response to expectations that have altered due to the loss of space perception and declined to a low level.

Symbolic data: During the process of socialization, the human learns specific behavioral patterns in addition to other acquisitions on how to use some spaces and respond to symbolic meanings of environmental stimuli. Thus, humans give meaning to some spaces, stimuli, and events in relation to cultural values of his or her environment and behaves based on them (Motalebi, 2005). Behaviors, as the process of doing any activity, have the following common features:

1. Perceptibility of behavior
2. Behavior evaluation
3. Individual or collective behavior
4. Predictability of behavior
5. Changeability of behavior
6. Dependence of behavior to the psychological space.

With increasing urban densities, more attention must be given to the provision of personal spaces. High densities are part of Brazilian urban models, however economic pressures act on the provision of appropriate personal spaces. Crowding occurs and these conditions can be linked to social problems. Behavioral consequences, such as aggression and crime rates may be linked to unfavorable spatial conditions. The architects and planners have the responsibility of creating buildings and urban fabrics that can communicate with its users and can be communicated by users. In this sense, they are also responsible for taking into account the mutual relationship between people and the built environment because as human beings, we regularly get contact with the physical environment which affects us and has influences on our behaviors.

5. The Impact of the Physical Environment on Human Behavior

5.1. The Impact of Architecture on Human Behavior

The shape and architecture of the building have an effect on the personality of the inhabitants. There is interaction between the urban framework and the human and many people exchange influence with the physical environment in which they live. Therefore, most of the treatments to solve the problems of the city were urban treatments. The careful observation of urban life gives an impression of the rudeness of social relations, the prevalence of individuality, the lack of precise knowledge and the lack of deep emotional involvement, despite the abundance of means of communication between individuals and groups and the importance of this communication in expanding the circles of interest, participation and outreach out of the narrow confines of the small community to the wider boundaries of society and humanity. The design process is capable of changing the habits, traditions and behavior of its inhabitants or users by using them for this origin (fig 2) (Altayash, n.d.).

Figure 2. Interrelationship of human behavior and urbanization and their impact on each other

It was, therefore, necessary to ensure that there is an appropriate amount of interaction within the small unit in the city (the neighborhood or neighboring neighborhood so that the communication becomes a fruitful and socially harmonious and supports the great impact of spatial proximity and the small number of connections in the region). The residential community is small, as it says that links to the residential area act as communication channels in which information and opinions are conducted. This process makes the life of the community more coherent. There is also a general assumption in city planning and construction that the first social contacts and the nucleus of social life consists of adjacent to residential, and the neighboring significant impact in determining the characteristics of the links (Kanani, n.d.). The various studies have influenced architecture and have led to the emergence of trends interested in the study of human behavior as a tool to design urban elements to meet social needs. When we want people to establish social relations, they must provide them with the age-old environment and its residential units so that these relations can take their place in the social environment (Abdul Hakim, 2009).

There are many influences that determine the nature of the interaction and the type of relations within the group.

Three main factors are mentioned:

- The length of time spent by individuals within a group, in a small group, relationships slowly form and become more permanent.
- Spatial proximity, where being in a specific small place facilitates contact and interaction with others face to face.
- Small numbers; small groups with limited numbers have a greater opportunity to document personal knowledge (Kanani, n.d.).

As any living creature, the most important thing is to meet the vital physiological and psychological requirements, which vary according to age, environment, culture and customs. Here, we find that architecture meets these requirements and promote urban development.

The function of the urban environment is linked to two objectives:

First, to achieve the physical aspect of creating spaces that act as content for activities. Second, the definition of the built environment as an environment surrounding the human and highlight that in the definition of the moral function of the built environment, man is the center of that environment and he or she affects and is affected by the built environment. This relationship is achieved through integration with the patterns of human behavior in which the design of these characteristics makes the connection to many psychological processes in humans. It can be said that the function of the environment with its material and moral dimensions is only the outcome of the design process of that environment's outputs and psychological processes by emphasizing the design goals of the built environment that are shaped by the intersection of psychological processes (cognition, knowledge and behavior) and elements and components that affect human behavior (Lang, 1974). Individual abilities, characteristics, social,

cultural and material framework (Fathy, 2001).

5.2. The Impact of the Urban Environment on Human Behavior

The physical environment can affect humans and can change according to the needs and behavior, hence the importance of the functional considerations of the activities and behavioral patterns within the place and the importance of the behavior of individuals and users within the vacuum (Fathy, 2001). This includes studying and analyzing the urban spaces and the surrounding physical environment and examining the possibility of change in accordance with the requirements of the users in light of the diversity of behavioral patterns of users as the full awareness of the nature of the activity comes from the determination of the surface that contains this activity functionally. Lynch 1960 also states that designers make the environment so that the user can do what he really wants or give him or her other opportunities for actions and reactions and these actions must be determined by vacuum and equipment. It can be said that the function should be appropriate to the available space in the sense that the analysis and design of spaces should be in a manner that achieves compatibility and harmony and balance and flexibility with the function that is required within the vacuum. There should also be a good understanding of behavioral patterns either through direct observations or indirect questioning. Building spaces and buildings cannot be viewed as mere contents of human activities but are integrated within human behavioral patterns so the built environment affects the behaviors of individuals and is affected by their presence in terms of choice of materials and moral dimensions (Lang, 1974).

6. Characteristics of the Physical Environment and its Relationship with the Characteristics of the Population in the Old Town of Jerusalem

This is done by describing the characteristics of the architectural dwelling and the characteristics of the population in different aspects of life and analyzing the correlation between these characteristics and the nature of the interaction between man and his or her living environment.

6.1. Physical Environment of the Dwelling

There is no doubt that the nature of the connection of the resident to his or her home affects the way he or she deals with the environment of the physical dwelling since it is the habit of the human being to take possession and ownership and to take care of what he or she owns. It turns out that the largest proportion of the population rent homes because they cannot afford to own a house. As a home-owner, this largely explains the deterioration of the situation of homes where the occupants are temporary and do not care to preserve them.

In terms of length of stay, the largest proportion of tenants who live in their homes is longer than 20 years of age. The lower expenditure on housing also explains the comfort of the housing provided by the larger segment. The decline helps to meet and provide the rest of the requirements of life but the concept of comfort here mostly means adaptation to living conditions because most of the population expressed that they only stay in these conditions due to their physical needs.

As for the physical characteristics of houses, it was found that the largest proportion of houses are currently stone. There are houses that consist of concrete material 7.2, which are modern buildings extraneous to the architectural heritage made of stone (Table 1).

Table 1. Building material in housing in the study area

Material	Percentage
Stone	53
Concrete	7,2
Stone of other material	39.8
Total	100

Figure 3. shows the quality of construction and stones used in the old town of Jerusalem

Since it is general knowledge that the buildings of the old town are built using stone, (Fig. 3), these buildings are cold in the summer and warm in the winter, so they can isolate the external weather and maintain a pleasant interior atmosphere. 64.1% of households use heat daily, 43.1% use heating appliances most of the time and 45.1% use them for at least 2 hours to 5 hours. These families report that their houses are very cold in winter while 58.5% of them use air conditioning, which is a fan in this case. The largest percentage of them, 59.5 %, of them also use air conditioners most of the time because of the fact that housing is too hot in the summer.

As for the entrances of the house, it was found that the largest proportion of the houses is the entrance of the family dwelling in a manor or a building. It also shows that the palace still contributes to the consolidation of relations between the neighbors. As for the number of floors that make up the house, most homes only have one floor (table 2).

Table 2. The number of floors that make up the house

Number of floors of the house	percentage
One	65%
Two	24,2%
Three floors	10.8
Total	100

The presence of the courtyard in more than 40% of the houses helps to alleviate the narrowness of the area and the house overlaps above the mansion on several floors where it is exploited by the residents to meet their various domestic needs where the dwelling with the inner courtyard of the family is one-story or two floors (Stallions, 2007). We find that a large proportion of houses in the old town of Jerusalem are condensed in an area estimated to be half the appropriate space needed. The sizes of houses are usually less than 50 square meters and this contributes to the narrowness of housing, loss of privacy for all members of this family, spread of diseases, and negatively affects the psychological state of children. The congestion within the house creates a sense of distress. Instead of being places where families can meet and reunite, houses are a source of discomfort that provide a sense of familiarity, affection and compassion among members of the same family (Halibi, 2008). It should be mentioned here that studies indicate that the living of a family of six people in two or three small rooms with a small area of the kitchen and bathroom leads to high mortality.

The research found that the houses in the old town of Jerusalem are overcrowded in terms of the number of individuals relative to the area of the house. There is no doubt that this has negative impacts because the family members participate in the allocations of the house and interfere in each other's privacy which causes tension. The overcrowded housing leads to the restriction of the individual's freedom leading to family disintegration and the isolation of people and the crowding in the house leads to the choice of children to stay in the street outside the home and thus leading to the problem of Tumble school.

Almost one-third of the families live in the temporary housing in the old town. About 35% believe that low-income housing in the Old City helps to plan life for the physical savings of purchasing an apartment outside the Old City.

Figure 4. The bad situation of some houses in the old town of Jerusalem.

A high proportion of housing suffers from moisture; humidity is the most prominent issue in the old town of Jerusalem where it was found that 94.8% of houses suffer from several forms of moisture. The walls, droppings, and smell of moisture in the house have been proven by studies that moisture and mold are associated with an individual's depression regardless of individual characteristics or other housing characteristics and thus affect physical health. However, the houses are also blessed with natural lighting as the sun shines strong in most of the rooms. This improves the internal environment within the house in terms of ventilation, natural lighting, availability of green and water elements, and protection against aerial, audio and visual pollution.

Most of the families in the region have relatives living in the same area as this was a large proportion of the residents of the area. Since the old town consists of many areas in the city, this means that there is a concentration of some families and their relatives in this area. There is also a lack of safety and the sense of danger and this indicates the weakness of family ties and social relations between relatives and knowledge. We note that the physical nature of the old town has a strong impact on the needs of individuals and that the lack of acquisition of the population of private vehicles to this day is the result of the structural nature of the complex that makes all services close. The study area of the city center is located nearby and accessibility on foot reduces the need to obtain a means of transport, which contributes to lower living costs in the region.

The schools of the majority of the population are located within the old town i.e. in the same area of residence or on its borders that is close to the students and a very small proportion of students are studying in private schools outside the old town that does not have this type of schools. The extent to which the physical environment of transportation can be adapted, as we know this environment was not prepared for it during the period of its establishment, shows that more than half of the houses cannot be easily reached by means of transportation. In the same direction, we find that the ambulance cannot reach the house in emergencies forcing them to carry the patient in need to reach the nearest accessible area for the ambulance. Most of the time, the courtyard in the dwelling no longer retains its functional and aesthetic features and is unfit to attract knowledge and neighbors. In this context, the physical environment of the built-up environment and the special urban nature of the old-age habitats in the

Old City strengthens the bonds between the population.

6.2. Physical Environment and Psychological Characteristics of the Population

The distortion of the old town is usually attributed to the lack of awareness among its inhabitants, including the lack of appreciation for the architectural value of the architectural elements in their dwellings and therefore the inadvertent destruction and destruction of the city's municipal windows. First of all, the residents of the first class, as a higher priority than the preservation of the architectural heritage itself, were responsible for the replacement of the damaged glass only by the supervisors of the municipality's work, but the vast majority of the population supported the removal of the intention Y traditional, this indicates a high rate of lack of awareness of the value of human architectural impact of the population, despite the conditions in which they live in a conflict of existence and identity with the occupier and despite the fact that most of them are aware of the occupier and settlers stealing this heritage and buy it.

6.3. The Future of the Old City According to the Behavior of the Population

The proportion of families that will remain in their home and will not leave during the next five years at least is 82%. The main determinant of whether or not to stay in the house was the economic situation. It was found that the large proportion of those who would remain in their homes remained the physical necessity since the old town became a refuge for the poor both inside and outside the city.

The greater proportion of the population will remain in their homes because of the physical necessity. At the same time, the larger percentage sees that they are comfortable in their homes. This indicates the ability of the residents of the region to adapt to the environment they do not belong to and also indicates the flexibility of the traditional dwelling that can meet the needs of the residents. As for the way people look at their residential environment, it has been shown that 30.2% of the population believes that the problem of the house is in the occurrence within the area of the old town, while the largest proportion of them do not see that there is a problem in the housing area. 72% believe that the problem is physical in the same dwelling, while 28% see no physical problem at home and this brings us back to two-thirds of the population who are satisfied with their home, explaining the physical state. In addition, 62% of the population does not see any problem in the neighborhood. On the contrary, half of this population, or more than a third of the population, refuse to have problems with the nature of the neighboring population.

The proportion of the population who believe that there is a problem in the negative social outlook towards the area of the Old City and its residents was a high percentage, which indicates that there is the so-called social isolation in the Old City of Jerusalem by the city's community. However, what alleviates this feeling on the population, according to their testimonies, is that most of their acquaintances are from the same region and, therefore, the situation is one, which creates the familiarity and belonging and the strength of social ties between them, but this leads to the reluctance to participate in social relations, especially outside the Old City.

6.3.1. The Population's Awareness of their Housing as Architectural Heritage and Cultural Identity

The study is concerned with the extent to which the residents of the region are interested because it reflects their awareness of dealing with them as they are the most important actors influencing their physical environment and thus their architectural heritage value. This also indicates the degree to which they will lose the old town - as an integrated heritage entity - its traditional architectural elements and thus its heritage spirit. The study showed that the largest percentage (87%) of the population would like to remain in their homes within the old city in case of restoration and maintenance work to solve their physical problems.

The largest consensus of the population (88.6%) desired to stay in their traditional homes if they were restored,

maintained and solved their physical problems. Third parties must bear the costs of rehabilitation. The reason for all the members of this group is the tightness that prevents them from maintaining them. At the same time, it is difficult for them to provide sufficient funds for housing in a more appropriate dwelling than the current one.

After this consensus comes second, they do not agree to take easy loans without interest. The main reason for this is the lack of stable or stable income for the family and therefore fear that it will not be able to pay the loan payments. The opinion consensus, which comes third, was surprising, with 47% of the population agreeing to completely demolish the traditional area and replacing them with modern residential buildings but only 8.51% of the population rejects the idea of demolishing traditional buildings because they are aware of their value not only for architecture and heritage but also for their importance. As a result, 46% of the population agreed to convert it into a purely tourist area and replaced it with modern-style dwellings outside the Old City. However, we find that as many as 6.50% of the population do not agree with this view. Of the population who answered that the issue of the region as a heritage does not really matter were (43%). On the other hand, 56.9% of the population is interested in the Old City area, and they object to the view that they do not care, and 30% strongly object.

The results of these statistics show that by taking a percentage of those who cannot determine their position on the concept of heritage and identity of the old town, we find that the percentage of those who have a cultural awareness of the value of the region is almost equal to the proportion of those who do not care about the subject area at all. The residents themselves have also pointed to the way they keep their homes and thus keep the Old City vibrant. They are improving the physical environment of their dwellings with external financing. They have mostly gathered that they want to stay in their homes if their physical environment is rehabilitated.

The study was conducted on the basis of research on the vulnerability of the physical environment of housing in the Old City of Jerusalem, the behavior of the population, the social, psychological, health and economic characteristics of the population and the region, and, conversely, does their personal qualities influence the surrounding physical environment and give it a special color.

As a result of their behavioral and personal qualities and the analysis of mutual relations, the author concluded that:

- The physical environment of the dwelling clearly affects the health characteristics of the population in terms of faster transmission of the disease among family members, as well as the obvious effect of the internal environment of the house from the mold and the fall of building materials. It's also affected by the lack of sunlight in the homes and, therefore, the cold inside the house with the inability of residents to have a source of heat.
- There is a clear impact on the physical environment on the psychological characteristics of the population and this confirms the scientific theories documented in the study, which assume that there is a negative impact of the home that suffers from the manifestations of moisture on the psyche of the population as the vast majority of housing in the Old City suffers from humidity.
- There is a clear relationship between the physical environment of the home and the educational attainment of children because of the overcrowding of the house from the lack of privacy and noise and the need for children to leave their schools. This is a reflection of the conditions of their poor families.
- There is a strong relationship between the physical environment of the majority of houses located within Israeli territory and between the consolidation of social ties between the neighbors.
- There is a clear relationship between the physical environment of adjacent homes and the low level of privacy in the population with more than one third of the windows of the houses overlooking the neighbors and Israeli territory.
- There is a direct and clear relationship between the poor economic conditions of the majority of the population in the old town and the continued depreciation of buildings and the worsening physical condition of homes. The study showed that the vast majority of the population wish to do maintenance work but the economic situation prevents that.
- Unfortunately, they are forced to use the easiest and most appropriate methods to suit the degree of their knowl-

edge, their awareness and their urgent need to rehabilitate the bad conditions of the house, which leads to the damage of the architectural character of the building and its cultural structure.

- There is a direct relationship between the administrative decisions of the Municipality of Medina and the poor environmental conditions in the Old City. - Housing within the Old City constitutes a temporary stage for more than one-third of the families and it further enhances that one-third of the families who believe that the low cost of living can save them from planning to own a modern apartment and get out of the house.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper has shown how a conceptual framework on environmental psychology can be drawn up and can be applied to the study of the importance of using human behavior while designing built environments. In the broader sense, this study suggests the use of behavioral sciences and their integration into theory and design practice. The lack of knowledge about human behaviors, attitudes and values is an important problem faced by architects and planners today in the design of built environments. In this regard, leveraging the knowledge of human behavior and the possibilities of behavior science provides designers with the possibility of integrating the social and individual aspects of people living in design processes (Churchman, 2002).

The architectural perception of the issues affecting the relationships between people and the environment is important in a creative and sensitive creative process. Investigation of the type presented here should be encouraged, particularly in the field of architectural education. Icon design from magazines and architectural prints provides access to diverse ammunition in diverse contexts.

In light of the study and analysis, the following results can be obtained:

- The physical environment of the homes in the Old City of Jerusalem affects the health aspects of the population.
- The architectural characteristics of the house affect the psychological characteristics of the population, especially the narrow space in most housing, which leads to the integration of private jobs resulting in violation of privacy and people refraining from participating in social relations, especially with residents from outside the region.
- The physical properties of the house threaten the scientific and professional future of the children of the families living in the old town.
- The prevailing structural system of houses located within the Israeli system in the Old City is still a social vacuum that affects the neighbors and encourages them to meet and socially interact, thus strengthening the bonds of relations between them despite the different ties of kinship and the current cultural backgrounds among them.
- The behavior of the population in turning the yards into a closed space has led to a decrease in the level of privacy of the population where the windows overlooking the neighborhood are adopted inside their homes.
- The majority of the population in the region has a poor economic level, which is the main reason for the lack of interest in the maintenance of their homes and thus the continued deterioration of the physical condition of the buildings and the threat of traditional tissue compact to the old town.
- Housing conditions in the Old City are worsening as they constitute a transitional temporary residence - not a target for stability.
- The poor physical condition of housing is devoted to the use of the poor class so that it has become attractive to the poor and uneducated groups from within and outside the city because of the low value of rent.
- The current situation in the Old City continues to promote social separation and discrimination towards its population by residents of many other neighborhoods of the city.
- The housing in the current poor physical conditions in the old city has worked to weaken the link between the human and the physical environment as it has become an environmental repellent for the financially able people.

8. Recommendations

- Directing financial support to private housing rehabilitation projects by convincing the financier of the closed link between the sustainability of the urban heritage area and the importance of the housing function in it as inhabited housing is the heart of life for the area whose environment is subject to abandonment and destruction.
- Financial support to preserve the architectural value of the houses as they constitute the majority of the integrated historical urban fabric that gives the region its importance and self-help projects through projects that are based on granting the population financial aid to carry out the necessary maintenance and repair work for the houses.

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